

MICROSCOPIC FRACTURE IN PARTICLE DISPERSED ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITE UNDER PLASTIC STRAINING

N. Kanetake and T. Choh
Department of Materials Processing Engineering, Nagoya University,
Furocho, Chikusaku, Nagoya 464-01, JAPAN

ABSTRACT

In order to directly observe microscopic phenomena during static stressing, the in situ tensile test in the SEM was carried out for two kinds of Al_2O_3 particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites produced with the melt stirring and powder extruding methods. The stress distribution in the composite during tensile loading was analyzed by an FEM calculation.

Some microcrack initiations are found in small plastic straining after yielding far before maximum loading point. The microcracks do not propagate because of ductility of the matrix, but a number of newly microcracking were developed during increasing strain. Most microcracks are occurred at the interface in the composite of the melt stirring method, while some microcracks in the particles are also observed in that of the powder extruding method. The calculated distribution of the internal tensile stress can explain the observed phenomena of microcracking.

Keywords: Metal matrix composite, Plastic deformation, Microcrack, FEM calculation

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) reinforced with particle dispersions are new structural materials which have high specific strength and may take the place of steel structures. When the MMCs are used as structural parts, they are subjected to some loading under various conditions. The MMCs can be deformed like conventional metals. Therefore, in order to put them to practical use for mass-products in the automobile or machine industries, their deformation processing may be possible. In applying deformation processing to MMC's, there are advantages in being able to use the existing forming techniques as they can reduce manufacturing cost of mass-products. However the MMCs are also subjected to hard stress conditions during deformation processing.

The particle dispersed MMC is consist of a ductile matrix metal, hard particles and their interfaces. It is predictable, therefore, that the internal stress and strain distributions under loading are much complicated as compared with conventional metals. Then microstructural degradation such as microcracking may be occurred due to the stress localization. And mechanical properties will become deteriorated in the strained composites. Recently, Lloyd[1] reported that the Young's modulus of SiC/6061 aluminum composites is reduced by plastically straining and that the reduction is owing to particle damage during straining. The authors[2] also reported that the strength of the forged SiC/6061 aluminum composite is decreased as compared with that before forging.

The influences of various factors of the matrix, particles and their interfaces on the microscopic degradation during stressing are very complicated and have not yet be hardly cleared. The authors [3] have tried to tensile test in-situ in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with a deformation stage, in order to directly observe the change in microstructure of the MMC under static tensile

Table 1. Composition of matrix aluminum alloy (wt%).

	Mg	Si	Fe	Cu	Cr	Zn	Mn	Ti	Al
Melt stirring	0.86	0.68	0.20	0.32	0.04	0.02	0.05	0.02	bal.
Powder extruding	1.11	0.60	0.42	0.34	0.19	0.01	0.01	-	bal.

loading. In the present work two kinds of aluminum matrix composites reinforced with spherical Al_2O_3 particles which are prepared using a melt stirring and a powder extruding methods are tested in the same way. Furthermore the internal stress distribution is calculated by a finite element method (FEM) and the calculated results are compared with the experimental observation.

2. PROCEDURES

2.1. Composite materials

Two kinds of aluminum matrix composites were prepared using a melt stirring and a powder extruding methods. The matrix aluminum is A6061 alloy whose composition is shown in Table 1 and the reinforcement is Al_2O_3 spherical particle whose mean diameter is $20\mu m$ and volume fraction is 10%. The spherical shape and relatively large mean diameter were employed for easy observation of the change of microstructures.

In the melt stirring method the molten aluminum mixed with Al_2O_3 particles was cast and hot extruded at 773K in the plate of 15x2mm, and in the powder extruding method the mixed powder was directly hot extruded also at 773K in the same plate.

2.2. Tensile test in SEM

The specimen for in situ tensile test in the SEM is shown in Figure 1, which has a narrow part in the center of a general tensile specimen. In order to continuously observe the change of microstructure, it's desired that the site where a crack initiates is specified. In that case, however, the crack occurs due to not only the microstructural fault but also the stress localization owing to the specimen shape. For specifying only cracking due to the microscopic fault, the specimen should be deformed under uniform stress state. The stress distribution in the center of the specimen shown in Figure 1 was estimated by an elastic-plastic FEM calculation under external tensile loading. In the calculation the specimen was assumed as an homogeneous material which has an elastic-plastic deformation property corresponding to the used composite material. From the calculated result, it was confirmed that no considerable difference but relative homogeneity in the tensile stress would be generated in the center area of the specimen.

In situ observation was carried out using a HITACHI S2300 Scanning Electron Microscope equipped with an INSTRON deformation stage. The deformation stage is enable to applying tensile and com-

Figure 1. Specimen used for in situ tensile test in SEM.

pressive loads according to a preliminary arranged loading path. A load(stress) -displacement(strain) curve is simultaneously measured using a data acquisition system with a personal computer. The specimen whose surface was polished is mounted in the deformation stage, and the static tensile load is applied to the specimen under constant displacement rate 0.1 mm/min. The loading and observation of microstructure are carried out simultaneously in situ in the SEM. The loading is stopped at appropriate points to be photographed. The other scanning electron microscope was also used to observe microcracks in detail. The static tensile properties was also examined using a general shape specimen and a tensile testing machine.

2.3. FEM calculation

An elastic-plastic finite element method was used to estimate the internal stress distribution in the composite. For the calculation a model composite material was assumed as shown in Figure 2, in which the spherical particles of 20µm in diameter were uniformly dispersed in an aluminum alloy matrix. The particles and the matrix are deformed elastically and elastic-plastically respectively. The elastic modulus of the particle was found in a literature for the Al₂O₃ and used in the calculation. The measured elastic-plastic stress-strain relation for the A6061 alloy produced with the same powder extruding method was used as a constitutive equation of the matrix in the calculation. The volume fraction of the particles is 10%, and the stress and strain distribution in an unit cell in Figure 2(a) were calculated under the external tensile loading using a mesh pattern shown in Figure 2(b).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Experimental Results

Figure 3 shows measured stress-strain curves of both composites. The flow stress and strength of the composite produced with the powder extruding method are higher than those of the melt stirring method, because fine oxide layers of aluminum powders are dispersed in the matrix and the grain size of the matrix may be finer.

Figure 2. (a): Composite model for calculation and (b): Mesh pattern in unit cell.

Figure 3. Nominal stress-strain curves of used composites.

Micrographs at two loading points A and B shown in Figure 3 are shown in Figures 4 and 5 for each composite. At the point A in small plastic straining after yielding, that is far before a maximum loading point, an initiation of the first few microcracks can be seen at the interface between the particle and the matrix in the both composites. The microcrack initiation can be found not only near a side edge of the specimen but also in the center area. From the micrographs at the point B near the maximum loading point, it can be found that the microcracks do not propagate because of ductility of the matrix, but a number of newly microcracking were developed during increasing strain. It is observed until just before fracturing. Many shear bands are also seen in the matrix, which means the considerable plastic straining of the matrix.

Most microcracks are occurred at the interface in the composite produced with the melt stirring method, while some microcracks in the particles are also observed in that with the powder extruding method. Some particles observed in fractur surfaces of both composites are shown in Figure 6 with a received particle. In the composite of melt stirring method very brittle fracture surface can be seen on the particle as Figure 6(b), though no special chemical compound was identified. While, in the case of cracking at the interface in the composite of powder extruding method, Figure 6(c), many dimples to prove ductile fracture can be seen on the particle, though a part of the as received surface can be also seen. It means that the bonding between matrix and particle is relatively strong in the powder extruding method, but the cracking at the interface is occurred owing to a part of incomplete bonding. When the bonding is complete all over the particle, the cracking in the particle occurs as shown in Figure 6(d).

3.2. Calculated results

Because almost all microcracks occur in the right-angled direction to the tensile direction, the cracking should be mainly related with an internal stress in the tensile direction, σ_y . Then the calculated distribution of the σ_y is shown in Figure 7. The Figure 7(b) shows the distributions along horizontal and vertical edges of the calculated unit cell. Those results are stresses at a mean external strain of 1.0%. A high tensile stress is generated on the equator of the spherical particle, and the high stress region is very narrow. The maximum tensile stress on the periphery is about 1.5 times as high as the inner part of the particle. The high tensile stress would cause the cracking in the particle which were seen in the composite of powder extruding method.

While, in the matrix, a relative higher tensile stress region can be found near the particle in the tensile direction. The higher tensile stress would be also related with the cracking at the interface. The stress value in the region is not so high and about 20% higher than that in the matrix far from the particle.

Figure 4. Micrograph of melt stirring composite during tensile loading.

Figure 5. Micrograph of powder extruding composite during tensile loading.

■ : 5 μm

Figure 6. Typical micrographs of particles after fracturing.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Calculated distribution of internal stress in the tensile direction σ_y .

However the cracking could be occurred at the incomplete bonded and the brittlely bonded interfaces.

4. CONCLUSION

When the particle reinforced aluminum matrix composite is subjected to static tensile loading, some microcrack initiations are found at the interface between the particle and the matrix in small plastic straining after yielding far before a maximum external loading point. The microcracks do not propagate because of ductility of the matrix, but a number of newly microcracking were developed during increasing strain. Most microcracks are occurred at the interfaces in the composite produced with the melt stirring method, and very brittle interface can be observed on the particle in the fractured surface. While some microcracks in the particles are also observed in the composite of the powder extruding method. On the particle cracked at the interface many dimples to prove relatively strong bonding between the matrix and particle.

The distribution of the internal tensile stress calculated with FEM model can explain the observed phenomena of microcracking. The maximum tensile stress on the periphery of the particle is about 1.5 times as high as the inner part. While, in the matrix, a relative higher tensile stress region can be found near the particle in the tensile direction, but the tensile stress is not so high as compared with that far from the particle.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to Mr. M. Nomura, Mr. H. Saiki and Miss R. Asano, graduate students of Nagoya University, for their cooperation in the present work, and this work was carried out under the Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research (B) in Japan.

References

1. Lloyd, D. J., Aspects of Fracture in Particulate Reinforced Metal Matrix Composite, *Acta metall. mater.*, Vol. 39, No. 1, 1991, pp.59-71.
2. Kanetake, N., Choh, T., Mechanical Properties of Forged SiC/6061 Aluminum Matrix Composite, *Proc. of 3rd Inter. SAMPE Metals Conference, Toront 1992*, pp.M414-M423.
3. Kanetake, N., Choh, T., Nomura, M., Microscopic Study on Deformation and Fracture of Particle Dispersed Aluminum Matrix Composites, *Proc. 2nd Japan Inter. SAMPE Symposium, Chiba 1991*, pp.788-795.